

People Identifiers

A decision tree to distinguish between the different types of persistent identifiers for people in a research context. The tree covers various considerations which were identified by FREYA partners. The information is not exhaustive and identifiers can be used for more than one purpose. It should also be noted that there are other types of identifiers for people but this tree focuses on those which are persistent and which are suitable for a research environment. Because some identifiers can be applied in various use cases, the options can repeat.

* STEM = Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics Researchers. HASS = Humanities, Arts and Social Sciences Researchers

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ORCID ID €

ORCID is a persistent identifier aimed specifically at researchers. It stands for Open Researcher and Contributor ID. It is an open identifier which researchers can sign up to. ORCID has a public API and a member API (to access and synchronise data).

ORCID is used by many services as an authentication mechanism and allows automated import of outputs into the ORCID account and can be used as an identifier hub.

Format: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5432-61169>

ISNI €

ISNI (International Standard Name Identifier, ISO 277729). It is designed to identify the public identity of persons and organizations and was conceived from the library and rights management community and the database has a high standard of curation. ISNI will be available in early 2020 via linked open data formats under CC0 as well as records for individual download.

Format: 0000 0001 2308 1542

WoS ResearcherID €

Formerly owned by Thomson Reuters, the WoS ResearcherID is now administered by Publons. This ID has a profile service.

Format: A-8720-2019

Scopus Author ID

Scopus Author IDs are assigned by Scopus to authors whose works are indexed in this database.

Format: 25521116500

Other People Identifiers

There are many other people identifiers, most developed by specific services such as Google Scholar, ArXivID. While these are used to ensure persistence between the different services, they are not used extensively beyond their own services.

€ Membership/Subscription Fees

All services with this symbol charge some sort of membership or subscription fee for full access to the service. Full access can include features such as minting the PIDs and API access. These fees can vary depending on the service and the type of organisation who wishes to use them. Many of the PID services which do not have membership or subscription fees require more technical resources from your organisation to set up and maintain the service.

For more information on People Identifiers

For more information on People Identifiers, including many more than are covered here, see this post on the PID Forum <https://www.pidforum.org/t/pids-forpeople/296> and also D3.1 Survey of Current PID services landscape <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3554254>

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